

ISic3475

I.Sicily inscription 3475

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

altar

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Centuripe, private collection (P. Cacia)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI336069

1. Μέλισσα Ζωπύρου.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645096

EDCS 64500536

PHI 336069

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 49.1275

Dubois, Laurent 2008. Inscriptions grecques dialectales de Sicile. Tome II..
Geneva. At 101

Manganaro, G. 1999. Sikelika: studi di antichità e di epigrafia della Sicilia greca.
Pisa, Roma. At 41 no.14 fig.91

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3475. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI
edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388640>